

Constraints Faced by the Entrepreneurs in SSI / MSMEs A Study in Theni District

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Abstract

SSI / MSMEs occupy a pivotal position in India's process of development. Since independence, these industries have made an all-round effort to boost the economy. The importance of the SSI / MSMEs sector is certainly an established fact and the sector may well be considered the backbone of the modern day economy. A conducive environment is created through the policies and interest of the government in economic and industrial development of the country. However due to unorganized nature of the SSI / MSMEs sector of these industries are also plagued by the problems of raw materials, labour, finance, marketing and power. Hence the present study has been undertaken to evaluate the various problems encountered by the entrepreneurs. The research results indicate that finance and marketing are the two important problems that affect the MSMEs in the study area. The findings generate a suggestion that a different set of policies and the promotional measures are important to support the entrepreneurship development.

Keyword: Problems, Entrepreneur, finance, Raw-materials, marketing, training.

Introduction

The problems of industries whether SSI/MSMEs or in the organized sector, are almost identical. The SSI/MSMEs, because of its weak financial structure and the limited resources, face the problems with difficulty. The respondent, therefore, has to view the entire spectrum of problems despite the great limitation under which the functions.

Statement of the Problem

Recognizing the important role that SSI / MSMEs play in the national economy, the central and state governments have taken active steps to promote and foster their growth. These measures have been particularly effective; but many of the problems of production, distribution and finance still continue to affect the SSI / MSMEs. While some of them are more or less common to a wide range of small industries, others have particular relevance to a group of industries situated in rural and backward areas. The problems of SSI / MSMEs are divided into external and internal. It is obvious, that the external problems arise from factors beyond the control of the entrepreneurs-the availability of power and other infrastructure facilities required for the smooth running of SSI / MSMEs. The internal problems affecting the micro small medium

enterprises relate to organisation structure and production channel, technical knowhow, training, industrial relations and inadequacy of management. The problems of industries whether in the small scale sector or in the organised sector, are almost identical. The micro small medium enterprises, because of its weak financial structure and the limited resources, face the problems with difficulty. It is in this context the present paper intends to probe the problems faced by the rural entrepreneurs.

Objectives of the Study

1. To analyse the constraints encountered by MSMES entrepreneurs.
2. To offer the valuable suggestions based on the major findings.

Sampling Design

As per the data available with the District Industries Centre, Theni, the sample district in Tamilnadu, has around 5375 MSMEs in Theni District during the study period. On classifying the MSME units, it was found that there were 1392 manufacturing industries, 2121 trading industries and 1862 service industries in Theni District. According to the All India Survey of MSMEs, at least 40 per cent of MSMEs put down their shutters permanently on various reasons. On enquiry with the officials of DIC, Theni a similar trend was prevailing in Theni District also and hence a total number of active MSMEs in the district would be around 3,225. In social science research a sample size of 10 per cent is found adequate to obtain meaningful inferences and hence in the present study also 10 per cent of the active units were chosen. Tippet's Random Sampling Numbers were used for selection of the respondents. Data were collected from all the 323 sample respondents through the interview schedules. Information collected from 23 respondents was found inadequate and hence effective sample size was fixed as 300. This includes 78 respondents from the manufacturing sector, 114 respondents from the trading sector and 108 respondents from the service sector.

Methodology

The present study is an empirical research based on survey method. The primary data were collected from the entrepreneurs with the help of a well - structured interview schedule. Before preparing the interview schedule, the researcher made a comprehensive review of the literature both directly and indirectly connected to the topic. The variables to be studied were identified by the researcher with the help of the officials of the Small Industries Development Corporation, District Industries Centre and the Tamil Nadu Industrial Investment Corporation. The secondary data were collected from journals, magazines, newspapers, books, documents, pamphlets and reports published by the commercial banks, Co-operative sector banks and the District Industries Centre.

Tools of Analysis

In order to bring out the most important problems faced by the respondents, data relating to the attitude of the respondents towards problems faced by them on the four factors, and the subsequent statements identified, were collected with the help of a pre determined and structured interview schedule. The marks assigned to the scales are 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The mean score on each statement obtained from the respective variables among the three types of business namely manufacturing, trading and service were calculated separately.

Constraints Faced By the Respondents

The problems of SSI/MSMEs are divided into external and internal. It is obvious, that the external problems arise from factors beyond the control of the respondents the availability of

power and other infrastructure facilities required for the smooth running of SSI/MSMEs. The internal problems affecting the SSI/MSMEs related to marketing, finance, raw material, labour, power supply, managerial guidance under utilisation capacities, guidance and counseling, officials, entrepreneurial technique and production.

Framework of Analysis

To find out the most significant factor which influences the respondent, Garrett’s ranking technique was used. As per this method, respondents have been asked to assign the rank for all factors and the outcome of such ranking have been converted into score value with the help of the following formula.

$$100(R_{ij} - 0.5) \text{ Percent Position} = N_j$$

Where

R_{ij} = Rank given for the i th variable by j th respondents

N_j = Number of variables ranked by j th respondents

With the help of Garrett’s Table, the per cent position estimated is converted into scores. Then for each factor, the scores of each individual are added and the total value of scores and mean values of the score is calculated. The factors having the highest mean value is considered to be the most important factor.

1. Problems Related to Marketing

The marketing of finished goods is one of the most important problems faced by the respondents. The researcher identified the problems relating to marketing that follow: 1. Competition from Small-scale units 2.Competition from Large-scale units 3.Slackness in demand 4.Other problems and 5. Not specifying any problem. The factors affect marketing and the mean scores are depicted in Table 3.1.

Table 1 Problems Related to Marketing

S.No	Problem	Garrett’s Mean Score	Rank
1	Competition from Small-scale Units	68.25	I
2	Competition from Large-scale Units	62.67	II
3	Slackness in Demand	55.89	III
4	Other Problems	49.41	IV
5	Not Specifying any Problem	42.60	V

Source: Primary data

Figures in parentheses denote percentages

Table -1 reveals that competition highest mean score of 68.25 and it ranks the first among the various problems. Competition from Large-scale units with the mean score of 62.67 and slackness in demand with a mean score of 55.89 hold the second and the third rank respectively. Other problems and not specifying any problem with the mean scores of 49.41 and 42.60 holds the fourth and fifth rank respectively.

2. Problems Related to Finance

It is difficult to carry out the activities of production and marketing without the adequate availability of finance. The above dictum can be substantiated by the statement that ‘money or credit is the lubricant that facilitates the operation of the marketing machine’. Finance is a problem

where the industrial activity involves high technology. When adequate finance is not available on time it will create trouble in the regular flow of production and marketing. The researcher identified the problem relating to finance that follows 1. Shortage of working capital 2. Shortage of fixed capital 3. High rate of interest 4. Red-Tapism in Government agencies 5. Meagre assistance from Government agencies 6. Other problems and 7. Not specifying any problems related to the finance. Table -2 shows the various problems relating to finance with the mean score and rank.

Table 2 Problems Related to Finance

Sl. No	Problem	Garrett's Mean Score	Rank
1	Shortage of Working Capital	70.61	I
2	Shortage of fixed Capital	68.02	II
3	High Rate of Interest	64.00	III
4	Red-Tapism in Govt. Agencies	60.66	IV
5	Meagre Assistance from Govt. Agencies	55.46	V
6	Other Problems	53.29	VI
7	Not Specifying any problem	52.75	VII

Source: Primary data

Figures in parentheses denote percentages

It could be seen from Table - 2 that the shortage of working capital is the most serious financial constraint for SSI/MSMEs, which ranked with a mean score of 70.61, followed by the shortage of fixed capital with a mean score of 68.02. while 'high rate of interest' ranked third with a mean score of 64.00, 'red-tapism in government agencies' ranked with a mean score of 60.66, 'meagre assistance from government agencies' ranked fifth with the mean score of 55.46, 'other problems' ranked sixth with the mean score of 53.29 and 'not specifying any problem' ranked seventh with the mean score of 52.75.

3. Problems Related to Raw Material

The Small-scale industrial units have to ensure timely and adequate availability of raw materials for continuous production. Small-scale industrial units are meant for better utilisation of local resources. Since raw material is the main requirement for production it has been taken as a variable. The researcher identified the problems relating to raw material that follow 1. high cost of material 2. Low quality of material 3. scarcity of material 4. Transport cost of material and 5. Inadequate storage facility. The aim of this analysis is to identify the foremost problem related to the raw material. Table -3 shows the various problems relating to raw material with their mean score and rank.

Table 3 Problems Related to Raw Material

Sl. No	Problem	Garrett's Mean Score	Rank
1	High cost of Material	62.08	I
2	Low Quality of Material	59.13	II
3	Scarcity of Material	57.34	III
4	Transport cost of Material	54.69	IV
5	Inadequate Storage Facility	50.95	V

Source: Primary data

Figures in parentheses denote percentages

Table 3 reveals that the high cost of raw material has the highest mean score of 62.08 and it ranks the first among the various problems relating to raw materials. Low quality of raw materials with the mean score of 59.13 holds the second rank. The scarcity of raw materials with the mean score of 57.34 holds the third rank. Transport cost of raw materials with the mean score of 54.69 and inadequate storage facility with the mean score of 50.95 holds the fourth and the fifth ranks respectively.

4. Problems Related to Labour

The aim of the researcher is to highlight the dominant variable whose impact is deep in a situation. Labour is a problem where the industrial activity involves high skill and technology. When skilled labour is not available it will create trouble in the regular flow of production. The researcher identified the following problems relating to labour that follow 1. Need for skilled labour 2. Lack of co-operation 3. Turnover 4. Absenteeism and 5. Not specifying any problem. The aim of this analysis is to identify the foremost problem related to the labour. Table 4 shows the various problems relating to labour with their mean score and rank.

Table 4 Problems Related to Labour

Sl. No	Problem	Garrett's Mean Score	Rank
1	Need for Skilled labour	65.83	I
2	Lack of co-operation	61.72	II
3	Turnover	58.90	III
4	Absenteeism	53.23	IV
5	Not Specifying any Problem	51.11	V

Source: Primary data

Figures in parentheses denote percentages

It is observed from the Table - 4 that being the high want of skilled labour has the highest mean score of 65.83 and it ranks first among the various problems related to labour. Lack of co-operation with a mean score of 61.72 and turnover with the mean score of 58.90 holds the second and the third ranks respectively. The absenteeism with the mean score of 53.23 and not specifying any problem with the mean score of 51.11 hold the fourth and the fifth ranks respectively.

5. Problems Related to Power Supply

There are a large number of villages where electricity is not available. The non availability of electricity is an obstacle in the way of SSI/MSMEs. Without power, production is not possible. Uninterrupted power supply alone can ensure the smooth flow of production. The causes of power supply problem in the study area is identified as: 1. High cost 2. Uncertain 3. Scarcity and 4. Other problems. The aim of this analysis is to identify the foremost problem related to the power supply. Table -5 shows the various problem relating to the power supply with their mean score and rank.

Table 5 Problems Related to Power Supply

Sl. No	Problem	Garrett's Mean Score	Rank
1	High Cost	67.80	I
2	Uncertain	62.10	II
3	Scarcity	54.49	III
4	Other Problems	51.09	IV

Source: Primary data

Figures in parentheses denote percentages Table -5 reveals that the high cost of the power supply with the highest mean score of 67.80 ranks the first among the various problems relating to the power supply. Uncertainty of the power supply with the mean score of 62.10 holds the score rank. The scarcity of power supply with the mean score of 54.49 and other problems with the mean score of 51.09 hold the fourth rank.

Findings

1. The major problem with SSI / MSMEs entrepreneurs is their lack of understanding of the procedural problems regarding applying for loans and availing of funds from the financial institutions.
2. Requirement of margin money restricts the young graduates to enter into the business.
3. Lack of rail transport facilities in rural areas increase the transport cost of raw material and marketing of finished goods.
4. Stiff competition from the large scale undertaking affects the marketing of rural enterprises.
5. The entrepreneurs depend upon the middlemen for marketing their products in order to avoid packing, transportation, advertisement, and sales promotion.
6. There seems to be ill planned training methodology and inconsistency in programme designing. These affect the result of entrepreneurial training.
7. Training content, sequence and theme and focus of the training is not developed according to the rural areas.

Suggestions

1. Procedures for applying bank loan must be simple and easy to understand by the micro, small and medium enterprises entrepreneur and unreasonable delay in sanctioning loans by financial institutions to be avoided by taking corrective measures.
2. In the case of first generation entrepreneurs, the financial institutions and banks may also consider feasibility of waiving collateral security, because engineers and graduates who come from poor family do not possess any land or other property.
3. Entrepreneurial development training covers the provision of motivational and managerial training.
4. Entrepreneur development programme will make an arrangement to support for establishment of the unit and would include provision of finance, infrastructure, raw materials, and machinery.
5. Adequate follow-up and counseling of the entrepreneur is also essential both during the implementation stage and when the unit starts commercial production. Re-orientation in the attitude of supporting organisations is called for.
6. Government should come forward to help the SSI / MSMEs in the form of direct purchase and sub contracting; setting up of permanent exhibition centers on the lines of head quarter of the district or in the form of such measures as will protect market for micro, small and medium enterprises.

Conclusion

SSI / MSMEs have been an effective instrument of progress and development in terms of industrialization of rural areas and a strong measure of tackling the problem of unemployment plaguing the masses and the country. Its role cannot be underestimated in a country like India. The Government will take necessary steps to achieve excellence in the formulation and implementation of industrial policies that aim at providing prompt and efficient services to the entrepreneurs for smooth implementation and successful operation of industrial projects. This will enhance the standard of living of the people through creating more employment and investment opportunities. Government will continuously strive further to simplify the procedures for industrial approval and impose only such minimum controls as are considered essential.

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